

D2.4 DATA GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

WP2, T2.2

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ABSTRACT

This deliverable presents the first version of the **SPOON Data Governance Framework**, developed to ensure trustworthy, interoperable, and citizen-centered data governance within the SPOON digital toolset. The framework builds upon European Union data regulations, especially GDPR policies. It is structured around **five key principles**: User Control, GDPR Compliance, Transparency and Trust, Ethical Handling, and Scalability and Interoperability. These principles guide and underpin the design of the framework's **five building blocks**: Strategy and Regulations, Data Policy, Data Ontology, Security and Access Control, and Ethics and Privacy.

The **SPOON digital toolset** is a suite of GDPR-compliant solutions for managing citizen-generated data in the SPOON's pilot regions, including DataU, the Questionnaire Tool, Personal Data Wallet, Data HUB, and Dashboard. Through the toolset, the data governance framework is operationalized to guarantee data quality, interoperability, ethical handling, and secure access. Finally, the framework also defines clear roles, responsibilities, and external governance models to support alignment with European Data Spaces, fostering long-term sustainability, openness, and responsible reuse of data.

DISCLAIMER

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TECHNICAL REFERENCES

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- *PU = Public
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D2.4 DATA GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

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ABBREVIATIONS

APIs	Application Programming Interface
BCIs	Behavior Change Interventions
CEADS	Common European Agricultural Data Space
CS	Citizen Science
CSL	Citizen Science Labs
CSOs	Civil Society Organizations
DGA	Data Governance Act
DSSC	Data Spaces Support Centre
FAIR principles	Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable
GDPR	General Data Protection Regulation
IoT	The Internet of Things
MFA	Multi-factor authentication
ODD	Open Data Directive
P2P	Peer-to-Peer
PDW	Personal Data Wallet
WP	Work Package

SUMMARY

The SPOON Data Governance Framework (see [Figure 1](#)) establishes a robust foundation for managing citizen-generated data collected in the SPOON's pilot regions using the SPOON digital toolset. Its purpose is to guarantee that data flows, from collection to sharing, are trustworthy, legally compliant, and citizen-centred. By integrating European regulations (especially GDPR), ethical standards, and FAIR principles, the framework aligns local practices with the broader European Data Strategy.

Figure 1 An Overview of SPOON Data Governance Framework

The framework is not only conceptual but also directly operationalized through the SPOON digital toolset. This ensures that governance principles are translated into the framework, categorized into 5 building blocks, and then applied in practice. The framework makes sure that the digital toolset supports user control, secure consent management, promote high data quality, and interoperability across research and innovation contexts.

Ultimately, the framework enables SPOON to build trust with citizens, empower them to stay in control of their data, and deliver high-quality, reusable datasets. By doing so, it strengthens the scientific value of the project and contributes to long-term sustainability and responsible data reuse in European food and health systems.

1 INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND AND PURPOSE

The global food system is under growing pressure. Climate change, biodiversity loss, and unsustainable diets threaten food security, making it harder for people to access safe, nutritious, and sustainable food. Extreme weather events such as droughts, wildfires, and pandemics further disrupt food supply chains (Fresco, 2009; Zurek et al., 2022). Urgent transformation is needed to address these challenges.

The SPOON project uses a paradigm shift to empower individuals in shaping a more inclusive and sustainable food environment through Citizen Science (CS). SPOON encourages healthier and more sustainable food choices across Europe by actively involving people in data sharing. To achieve this, the project integrates behavioral science, data-driven interventions, and digital tools, ensuring that food-related data is shared ethically and securely.

To bring this vision to life, eight work packages (WPs) work together in a coordinated effort, with WP2 plays a crucial role in supporting project pilot partners by developing the digital toolset and support its co-creation with citizens on the ground through CSLs, kick off its roll out through BCIs, and later on broader deployment of the digital toolset to collect and analyze personal food data, and promote healthier food choices. The CSLs, BCIs and the large-scale deployment of the digital toolset are key activities that will be implemented in 6 project pilot regions, namely, Braunschweig, Germany; Thessaloniki, Greece; Turin, Italy; Bruges, Belgium; Valencia, Spain; and Pomurje Region, Slovenia.

The main objective of WP2 is to co-develop and test the SPOON toolset, including DataU, Questionnaire Tool, Personal Data Wallet (PDW), Data HUB, and Dashboard. At the heart of WP2 is T2.2, which focuses on data governance. A strong data governance framework is essential for ensuring that food data is handled securely, ethically, and in compliance with regulations. **Key objectives of T2.2 include:**

- Establishing **data security and protection** protocols in compliance with the General Data Protection Regulation (**GDPR**) and other relevant regulations.
- Ensuring **high data quality standards** and interoperability for seamless data exchange.
- Addressing **ethical and privacy challenges** in Citizen Science data collection.
- Defining strategies for **integrating SPOON data** with European Data Spaces and digital infrastructures.

T2.2 defines clear guidelines for data sharing, interoperability, data quality, and risk management, ensuring smooth collaboration across different WPs. It also tackles ethical concerns and privacy challenges, while supporting integration with European Data Spaces to enhance data-sharing capabilities.

This deliverable, **D2.4 “SPOON Data Governance Framework v1”**, provides the first version of a framework for secure, ethical, and interoperable management of citizen-generated food data. It is exploratory and will refine and extend the governance model in line with CSL pilots, WP1 surveys, and toolset development progress.

1.2 SPOON IN THE BROADER EU CONTEXT

The transformation of the food system requires collaboration across multiple sectors, using data-driven solutions and citizen engagement to drive change. The SPOON project is part of a broader European effort to create a more sustainable, resilient, and data-driven food system.

To achieve this, citizen-generated food data must be securely shared, accessed, and utilized while ensuring privacy and ethical compliance. That is why the T2.2 data governance framework is designed to integrate with European Data Spaces, aligning with EU-level strategies such as the Food 2030 Framework and other European data-sharing initiatives (See [Table 1](#)).

The Food 2030 Framework guides research and innovation for food system transformation. Its pathways most relevant to SPOON are:

- Data & Digital Transformation – using data spaces and digital tools for better food governance.
- Nutrition & Sustainable Healthy Diets – enabling research on healthy, sustainable consumption.
- Governance for Food Systems Change – giving citizens control and ensuring transparency.

SPOON also aligns with the European Data Strategy, the GDPR, the Data Governance Act, and the Data Act, which together ensure that data flows securely while respecting privacy, sovereignty, and fairness.

To operationalize these principles, SPOON leverages several initiatives developed by its partners. They provide consent management, trusted sharing, and federated access models that inform the project’s digital toolkit and link it to the emerging European data-space ecosystem.

[Table 1 Key EU Policies, Frameworks, and Initiatives Linked to SPOON](#)

Initiative / Framework	Purpose & relevance to SPOON	Key features
GDPR	Legal basis for personal-data protection and privacy.	Principles: lawfulness, fairness, transparency, data minimisation, storage limitation.
Data Governance Act / Data Act	Rules for trustworthy intermediaries, data re-use, and rights/obligations for access & use.	Complement GDPR; enable cross-sector data flows with clear governance.
Food 2030 Framework	EU R&I agenda for sustainable food systems.	11 pathways to guide future research and innovation policy reflections related to Horizon Europe, the farm-to-fork strategy, the European Green Deal and beyond.

European Data Strategy	Vision for a single EU data market ensuring interoperability and trust.	Supports creation of domain-specific data spaces.
DataU	Citizen-centric consent and data-sharing platform.	GDPR-compliant, interoperable; integrated with SPOON to manage participant consent.
Digital Wallet (PDW)¹	Stores participants' personal info securely, separate from public data lake.	Based on eIDAS & WE BUILD work on wallets for agrifood data sharing.
DjustConnect	Trusted agrifood data-sharing platform (EV ILVO).	Regional data space; farmers control access; supports EU Common Agricultural Data Space.
DIH Agrifood Data Space	National hub for federated access and governance (ITC).	Digital Innovation Hub; supports experimentation and scaling via i4Trust, FIWARE.
GAIA-X	Pan-European federated data-infrastructure project.	Principles of openness, transparency, sovereignty; supports decentralised identity and trust services for agri-food actors.

1.3 DOCUMENT SCOPE AND STRUCTURE

This deliverable, titled “*SPOON data report v1*”, presents the first version of the SPOON Data Governance Framework. This deliverable supports WP2 objectives by outlining principles, structures, and mechanisms that help ensure the trusted, ethical, and interoperable use of citizen-generated food data.

This deliverable looks at how data is governed within the SPOON digital toolset and CSLs. Furthermore, it also places these governance methods in the wider European context, such as the EU Data Strategy, Food 2030 pathways, and new European data spaces. We look forward to exploring broader EU-wide governance models in future updates.

The structure of the deliverable is as follows:

- **Chapter 1** introduces SPOON, T2.2 objectives, and EU context.
- **Chapter 2** describes the SPOON digital toolset and its integration with European data spaces.
- **Chapter 3** outlines the conceptual foundations of data governance and introduces the SPOON framework.

¹ Similar wallet solutions have been developed in other EU projects. SPOON's PDW adapts these prior implementations to the project's consent model and integration with DataU, the SPOON Dashboard, and the DataHub.

- **Chapter 4 to Chapter 8** detail the five building blocks of the framework: Strategy & Regulations, Data Policy, Data Ontology, Security & Access Control, and Ethics & Privacy.
- **Chapter 9** concludes the deliverable with a summary and outlook.

2 DATA IN SCOPE

In SPOON, data is generated from multiple sources. For the purpose of this report, we focus on the key activities directly linked to the data governance framework: the Citizen Science Labs (CSLs) and the Behavioural Change Interventions (BCIs). Together with European citizens and food stakeholders, these activities generate data on consumption behaviours and local food environments.

In addition, large-scale deployment of the SPOON digital toolset enables engagement beyond CSL/BCI participants, raising awareness and empowering healthier and more sustainable food practices, while also generating data that supports food policy and decision-making.

Specifically, we pay more attention to these three main sources:

- **The CSLs:** Data collected from participants in different regions.
- **The SPOON digital toolset:** Data generated through the questionnaire, DataU, Wallet, SPOON Dashboard, and Data HUB.
- **WP1 survey:** Data collected to explore barriers and drivers for sustainable and healthy food consumption, based on research gaps and CSL input.

The table below ([Table 2](#)) summarizes the types of data involved, and with links to the digital toolset and storage components:

Table 2 Overview of data types in SPOON

Type of Data	Explanation	Link to SPOON Digital Toolset
Consumer behavior data	How people plan, buy, store, prepare, eat, and dispose of food	Collected via multi-media questionnaire, and stored in Data Hub (if consent is given)
Food-related data	Food habits (products, diets, menus, environments) and food characteristics (type, quality, quantity)	Collected via multi-media questionnaire, and stored in Data Hub (if consent is given)
Demographic data	Age, gender, education, household type; collected in harmonised formats (e.g., ranges for age)	Collected via multi-media questionnaire, and stored in PDW and DataHub (if consent is given)
Consent of data	Records of consent	Managed in DataU and Dashboard

Personal/sensitive data	Data that may identify individuals (e.g., demographics, behaviour); no highly sensitive data planned for now	Stored securely in PDW
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To make this clear, we need input from:

- T2.1 (WP2): to describe in detail how the toolset collects and processes data.
- WP3/WP4 (CSLs): to explain what types of data they collect in their regions.
- T1.2 (WP1): to provide updates about their survey, which is expected around October.

3 SPOON DIGITAL TOOLSET

3.1 SPOON DIGITAL TOOLSET

One of the key ambitions of WP2 is to build trust in data sharing. To do this, SPOON offers citizens not just tools, but a transparent, user-friendly, and GDPR-compliant digital ecosystem that makes participation safe, meaningful, and empowering. This ecosystem is designed with scalability in mind, connecting to other European data spaces (Please see Section 3.2) through APIs, so that citizen-generated food data can seamlessly contribute to the wider Agri-Food Value Chain transformation.

The SPOON Digital Toolset (see Figure 2) is a suite of interconnected digital solutions designed to empower citizens, researchers, and policymakers in transforming food systems through data-driven innovation, citizen science, and secure digital interactions. By ensuring GDPR compliance, transparency, and user control, the toolset allows individuals to actively participate in research and decision-making while maintaining full sovereignty over their personal data.

Figure 2 An overview of the digital tools and connected dashboards

Each tool plays a distinct role but is expected to seamlessly integrate, creating a cohesive and secure digital ecosystem:

- **DataU** – A GDPR-compliant consent management platform that ensures all data-sharing activities are transparent, secure, and fully user-controlled. It enables citizens

to grant, track, and revoke consent for their data via a centralised interface called ‘DashboardU’.

- **Questionnaire Tool (QT)**– A customizable digital survey platform designed to collect citizen-generated data on food consumption habits, preferences, and behaviours.
- **Software Development Kit (SDK)** - for developers of applications that would like to connect their application to DataU for GDPR compliance.
- **Personal Data Wallet (PDW)** – A personal, encrypted repository where citizens can store, manage, and selectively share their food-related data.
- **SPOON Data Hub (SDH)** – A repository for anonymized datasets collected from the utilisation of the SPOON multi-media questionnaire
- **SPOON Dashboard (SD)** - a user interface to access several applications connected to DataU.

The data journey (see [Figure 3](#)) within the toolset typically follows these steps:

- Step 1: Based on Questionnaires (as defined by the project researchers) and consent to share data (by the citizens), the PDW and the SPOON database (SDB) are filled.
- Step 2: Based on DataU-connected third-party applications and consent to share data, the PDW and the SDB are filled by citizens.
- Step 3: Analysis of data will be done by researchers, and based on consent (by the citizens) to share anonymised data, personal data will be anonymized (by the researchers) and stored in the Data HUB.
- Step 4: Citizens can view their shared data in the PDW and the SPOON Database and anonymised data in the publicly accessible SPOON Data HUB.

Figure 3 The Digital Toolset Integration Used in the Data Journey

For further technical information about the toolset, please check D2.1 Specifications for SPOON digital toolset v1.

3.2 EUROPEAN DATA SPACES INTEROPERABILITY

While the SPOON Digital Toolset operates as an independent ecosystem, it will become more powerful when it becomes interoperable with other systems. When data can be shared, identification and consent systems are in line with certain standards, and certain tools from the toolkit can also be used for other projects or use cases, this enhances the added value of the work done in the project. During the Spoon project, a connection will be made with the broader network of European Data Spaces. These connections ensure that citizen-generated food data can have a meaningful impact beyond the project, improving innovation and research in the agri-food sector, and potentially influencing EU-wide policies.

At a technical level, the SPOON toolset achieves this integration through APIs, interoperability standards, and semantic alignment. Each tool is built with FAIR data principles and interoperable data standards, such as Linked Data, to ensure interoperability. All these alignments will enable smooth data exchange to share project data with other initiatives or integrate external data with the Spoon toolkit, using initiatives as data platforms DataU, DjustConnect in Belgium, and DIH data sharing infrastructure in Slovenia, connecting it to the Common European Agricultural Data Space (CEADS).

Examples of integration in practice include:

- DataU's API layer enables other EU data spaces to request and verify citizen consent in real-time, without storing personal data themselves.
- The SPOON Data HUB can publish anonymized datasets in formats and vocabularies compatible with other European initiatives, allowing these datasets to be aggregated at the EU scale for research and policy analysis.
- The PDW supports standardized data export/import formats (e.g., DCAT, JSON-LD), enabling citizens to transfer their own data between SPOON and other compatible platforms.

4 DATA GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

4.1 DEVELOPMENT PROCESS

The development of the SPOON Data Governance Framework follows an iterative and participatory approach. The process started with a review of relevant literature and existing frameworks related to data governance, particularly in the context of citizen science and data spaces (e.g., DSSC, Agri-data spaces). Based on this desk research, a basic structure was proposed, covering key areas such as data policy, ontology, security, and ethics.

Input from SPOON partners, including CSLs and WP/Task leads, has been gathered through meetings, shared documents, and working tools (Mural dashboard) during the first workshop. The framework is therefore not static, but evolves step by step. Planned activities, such as dedicated ontology sessions, will further contribute to its refinement (see [Chapter 7](#)).

First workshop for the framework

An important milestone was the first ‘SPOON Workshop on the Data Governance Framework’, held on 4 July 2025. The objectives of the workshop were to:

- Align understanding and expectations of the SPOON Data Governance Framework among partners.
- Gather input on key building blocks and aspects such as data quality, privacy, interoperability, and ethics.
- Define priorities for the first version and discuss possible improvements for future iterations.
- Explore how the framework connects with the SPOON digital toolset.

The results of the workshop

The workshop was successful in bringing together perspectives from different disciplines and perspectives. These insights from the workshop have been taken into account in the current version of the framework, and they will continue to inform its development (see [Figure 4](#)).

Other important recommendations are listed:

1. The need for participatory ontology development to ensure that categories and terms reflect real practices in the project pilot regions.
2. Guidance for governance in participatory settings. This requires clear rules and responsibilities in the framework.
3. The integration of multi-level governance elements, alignment between local, national, and EU-level governance mechanisms for citizen-generated data.

Figure 4 The Feedback for Framework Building Blocks

Future workshops are planned to ensure that feedback from the pilot partners and the wider consortium is systematically integrated. The next workshop will be scheduled before the next framework iteration to ensure that the framework remains both practical and co-created.

4.2 THE CONCEPTS AND RELEVANCE OF DATA GOVERNANCE

Before we go further, it is important to clarify the difference between data governance and data management.

What they mean?

Data management is the operational aspect of data governance, which means how we handle this data every day: collecting, storing, cleaning, using, and disposing it (Sebastian-Coleman, 2013). **Data governance**, on the other hand, is a broader concept. It is about the rules, policies, roles, and responsibilities that make sure data is handled properly across the organization. It is the exercise of decision-making and authority for data-related matters (Plotkin, 2020).

Importance for SPOON

Data governance is essential for SPOON due to its focus on transforming food systems through data-driven innovation and citizen science, particularly involving personal data.

1. **Ensuring Security, Ethics, and Compliance:** A strong data governance framework is essential for handling food data securely, ethically, and in compliance with regulations. SPOON is designed to be fully GDPR-compliant to ensure that personal data is managed with explicit, dynamic, and revocable consent and privacy is protected by design. The framework establishes data security and protection protocols in line with GDPR and other relevant regulations.

2. **Facilitating Data Sharing and Interoperability:** A key objective is to agree on a standard data ontology, which is crucial for the development of the digital toolset. This involves developing inclusive data ontologies together with stakeholders in workshops to capture the complexity of food systems and citizen science activities. We also leverage open standards and existing ontologies to ensure interoperability.
3. **Promoting Trust and Citizen Empowerment:** Citizens are often suspicious about sharing data due to privacy concerns (Trein & Varone, 2024). SPOON directly addresses this by aiming to increase citizens' confidence in sharing personal food data through transparent, easy-to-use, GDPR-compliant digital tools (DataU) and a well-structured data governance framework.
4. **Alignment with EU Initiatives:** SPOON's data governance framework is designed to integrate with European Data Spaces, the Digital Wallet and new legislation (Data Act, Data Governance Act). This ensures the project's approach contributes to a broader vision of responsible data sharing in the food system.

Why a Framework matters?

A framework defines a set of ideas, conditions, or assumptions that shape how a topic is structured, understood, or approached (Merriam-Webster, n.d.). Unlike a detailed plan or procedure, a framework provides a structured map of what is important, how the parts relate, and which actors are responsible for decision-making.

In the context of SPOON, the Data Governance Framework serves exactly this purpose. It brings together the main governance principles, the roles of different actors, and the connections between policies, ontology, data quality, and ethical safeguards. It is not about listing every dataset or technical detail, but defining the rules and relationships that guide how citizen-generated data is handled across the SPOON digital toolset in a systematic way.

For SPOON, this framework ensures that decisions about food data follow a shared structure, which helps build trust and consistency. It also helps all partners, from pilot implementers to technical leads, to operate with the same understanding of responsibilities and rules.

Beyond the project, the framework has broader relevance. Many citizen science initiatives face the same challenge: how to handle sensitive, participant-generated data in a trustworthy, ethical, and compliant way. The SPOON framework can therefore serve as a reference model for future projects in the food domain and beyond, supporting alignment with European Data Spaces and other citizen science infrastructures.

4.3 THE SPOON DATA GOVERNANCE FRAMEWORK

The SPOON Data Governance Framework is a foundational element of the project. It ensures that food data collected in the SPOON digital toolset is handled securely, ethically, and in line with European values and regulations. The framework provides guidance for data policy, ontology, quality, security, and ethics. It also serves as a reference for collaboration between the different tools and work packages.

4.3.1 Key Governance Principles

The framework is based on five key principles. These principles are aligned with the project objectives and work plan, by the European framework, insights from European projects such as AgriDataSpace, Foodity, FoodDataQuest, Data4Food2030, ScaleAgData, CEADS, and scientific literature on citizen science and data (Baungard et al., 2021; Stilgoe et al., 2013; Tauginienė et al., 2020; Wilkinson et al., 2016). They are translated into building blocks of the framework to ensure they are implemented in data governance activities with the CSLs.

The 5 key principles are:

User Control: In SPOON, the main users are the citizens who participate in the CSLs, the BCIs as well as broadly users of the SPOON digital toolset. They are asked to share personal and data about their food choices and daily life. For this reason, data sovereignty and control must stay with the citizen. Literature on citizen science highlights that participants are more motivated and more willing to share data if they know they keep ownership and control (Ganzevoort et al., 2017; Shah et al., 2019). In SPOON, this is achieved through the PDW, where citizens can decide what data to share and for what purpose. This first principle is also closely linked to all the following ones.

GDPR Compliance: The GDPR is the main legal framework for personal data protection in the EU. It sets strict requirements on informed consent, purpose limitation, and data minimization (European Union, 2016). Compliance with GDPR is essential because the SPOON digital toolset processes personal data from citizens. Therefore, the framework requires that every step of the data flow, from collection to storage, follows GDPR principles, which means that all data-sharing activities in SPOON need to be fully compliant with the GDPR principles to ensure the lawful and secure processing of citizens' personal data.

Transparency and Trust: Trust is fundamental for citizen participation. Evidence from research on participation and public engagement shows that clear and operational transparency helps build and sustain trust (Eleta et al., 2019). Studies show that citizens are more likely to join and share data when the processes are transparent and open (Dean Allemang & Bobbin Teegarden, 2017). By fostering trust in data sharing, the Data Governance Act (DGA) also indicates that it helps the development of Common European Data Spaces (European Parliament and the Council of the European Union, 2022). In SPOON, transparency is achieved by giving citizens clear information on how their data is collected, processed, and shared. Mechanisms such as consent management, the use of blockchain technology, and access dashboards support transparency by giving participants visibility and control over their data (see *Ethics & Privacy* building block for details on consent). This helps to build trust between citizens and researchers (Leible et al., 2019).

Ethical Handling: Beyond legal compliance, ethical principles such as European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity and AI Act must guide the use of data. In addition, the project has its own DMP that is guiding all partners data management, including ethical handling practices. Research ethics literature also underlines that citizen data should be collected and used with respect, fairness, and accountability (König, 2021). In SPOON, this means that data governance must be transparent, explainable, and non-discriminatory, and aligned with the

values of integrity and openness. Ethical handling is also about protecting participants from harm and ensuring that benefits are fairly shared across the community (Bromley et al., 2015).

Scalability and Interoperability: To ensure long-term impact, the framework must be scalable and interoperable with European Data Spaces and existing infrastructures. In SPOON, FAIR principles are applied, and the data governance framework is designed to facilitate integration with European initiatives. This increases the value of citizen-generated data and ensures that it can be used in future projects.

4.3.2 Building Blocks of the Spoon Data Governance Framework

The SPOON Data Governance Framework is composed of five interconnected building blocks, including **Strategy & Regulations**, **Data Policy**, **Data Ontology**, **Security and Access Control**, and **Ethics and Privacy**. **Strategy & Regulations** set the alignment with European frameworks and ensure compliance. **Data Policy** defines how data is collected, documented, and shared. **Data Ontology** provides the common language and structure for interoperability. **Security and Access Control** ensure that data is protected and that access is managed fairly. **Ethics and Privacy** establish principles of trust, transparency, and responsible use. In each building block, there are several sub-building blocks to explain what needs to be addressed from this perspective (See [Table 3](#)). Each building block is described more in detail in the following chapters.

Table 3 The Building Blocks of the Data Governance Framework

Building Blocks	Sub-building Blocks	Application in SPOON
Strategy & Regulations	EU Data Regulations	Applying EU legal regulations/standards to all SPOON data activities
	Roles and Responsibilities	Clear definition of roles and responsibilities for actors and stakeholders
	Aligned with External Governance Models	Mapping framework and toolset to European frameworks and models to ensure compatibility
Data Policy	Data Management	Daily operations for managing data according to the DMP.
	Data Quality	Procedures for validating completeness, consistency, and timeliness
	Data Interoperability	Enabling toolset to exchange and reuse data via common APIs, formats, and protocols.

	Data Sharing	Rules and processes for giving access to internal/external users
Data Ontology	Standardized Vocabularies	Controlled terms (e.g., categories) to keep meaning consistent across SPOON
	External data ontology models	Using existing ontologies to align terminology with the wider community.
	Participatory Ontology Development	Validating and co-creating terms with CSLs, stakeholders, and experts to reflect local food realities.
Security and Access Control	Data Security Measures and Access Control	Technical measures and policies to restrict access based on roles.
	Data Protection	Technical safeguards for handling (personal) data.
	Risk Management	Identifying risks and defining mitigation steps.
Ethics and Privacy	Ethical Principles	Applying EU and national ethical principles.
	Data Privacy	Ensuring personal information is processed lawfully, fairly, and kept confidential.
	Consent management and data minimization	Tools (e.g., DataU) for granting/revoking consent; collecting only what is strictly necessary.

5 STRATEGY AND REGULATIONS

5.1 EU DATA REGULATIONS

EU Data Regulations provide the overarching legal and policy framework governing the collection, processing, storage, sharing, and reuse of data across the European Union. For people who generate data to SPOON, alignment with these regulations is essential to ensure compliance, protect individual rights, and enable responsible and interoperable data sharing across local, national, and EU levels.

Key EU regulations relevant to SPOON include:

- **General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR):** The main framework for personal data protection in Europe. It sets out strict requirements on transparency, informed consent, purpose limitation, and data minimization, ensuring that citizens retain control over their personal data.
In SPOON, GDPR principles are implemented through dynamic consent forms (via DataU), purpose limitation in the Questionnaire Tool, and privacy-by-design storage in the PDW.
- **Data Governance Act (DGA):** Establishes mechanisms for secure and trusted data sharing, including the role of data intermediaries and data altruism frameworks.
SPOON applies the DGA by using intermediaries (APIs) for trusted exchange and by defining clear reuse agreements for citizen-generated datasets.
- **Data Act:** Defines rights and obligations around access and use of data, especially non-personal and Internet of Things (IoT) data, while promoting data portability and interoperability across sectors.
SPOON reflects the Data Act through interoperability protocols in the Data Hub and by ensuring that participants can easily access or transfer their data.
- **AI Act:** Introduces risk-based requirements for AI systems to ensure transparency, human oversight, and ethical safeguards in AI-driven data processing, which will apply to SPOON where AI-based analytics are developed.
- **FAIR Principles (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, Reusable):** Although not a regulation, the FAIR principles form a cornerstone of EU data policy. SPOON integrates these principles to ensure that citizen-generated data can be responsibly shared, reused, and connected across European data spaces.

Within the governance framework, EU regulations are operationalized through policies on data quality, provenance, security, ethics, and privacy. The compliance of these regulations is ensured through clear procedures for data collection, data storage, data sharing, obtaining informed consent, and anonymization. GDPR's principles of data minimization and purpose limitation are reflected in how the Questionnaire Tool only collects what is truly necessary, while the PDW ensures storage and sharing are always under the citizen's control. Consent management is handled dynamically through the DataU platform. Citizens can update or withdraw their consent at any time. This means citizens can actively manage personal information via the SPOON Dashboard.

Within the project, regulatory alignment is further supported by the Data Management Plan (DMP) and targeted capacity-building activities, ensuring that all actors involved in data collection and management understand and adhere to relevant EU rules.

5.2 ROLES AND RESPONSIBILITIES

Clear roles and responsibilities are established to ensure that citizen-generated food data is handled securely, ethically, and in compliance with EU and national regulations. The framework adopts a data stewardship approach, assigning explicit responsibilities across different actor types and all stages of the data lifecycle.

General data governance principles are designated within each actor group to oversee lifecycle management, data quality, compliance with regulations, and participatory governance. These actor groups refer to citizen scientists, pilot coordinators, researchers, and other relevant governance bodies. These principles are embedded in a multi-level governance structure, so we also define the roles and responsibilities across all decision-making levels within the project. Please see [Table 4](#) below for further details.

Table 4 Key Roles and Responsibilities within SPOON

Roles with RACI format	Responsibilities
Project Coordinator (CSCP) -A/C/I	Overall responsibility for proper implementation of the project, compliance with the Grant Agreement, liaison with the granting authority, and high-level oversight of data governance.
Digital Toolset Developer (JIBE) – R/C/I	Develops and tests the SPOON digital toolset; co-develops with SPOON partners (esp. pilot coordinators through CSLs); CSL researchers manage and use the toolset in practice; JIBE provides operational and technical support for the toolset and ensures continuous operation.
Data Governance Framework Developer (EV ILVO) – R/C/I	Designs the common SPOON data governance framework, integrates GDPR principles, sets data quality standards, and manages ethical issues.
Pilot Coordinators (CSLs, BCIs, deployment of digital toolset) – R/C/I	Manage data collection, citizen engagement, consent management, and provide feedback on tool usability.
Citizens (Data Subjects and co-developers) – R/I	Provide personal food data, manage consent via DataU, approve anonymization before data enters the Data Hub, participate in co-creating questionnaires, and provide feedback to improve tools during workshops.

Researchers in the project – R/I	Co-design questionnaires, anonymize datasets, and analyze data for behavior change interventions and policy recommendations.
All Consortium Members – R/I	Adhere to ethical principles, legal obligations, and security protocols; maintain accurate records; ensure confidentiality of personal and sensitive data.

Note: RACI format is a RACI matrix, who is responsible, accountable, consulted, and informed for every task in a project.

- *R (Responsible): Executes the task or process.*
- *A (Accountable): Ultimately answerable for correct completion.*
- *C (Consulted): Provides input or expertise.*
- *I (Informed): Kept updated on progress and decisions.*

5.3 ALIGNED WITH EXTERNAL GOVERNANCE MODELS

5.3.1 Reference models

SPOON’s governance design does not exist in isolation. It is informed by both domain-specific initiatives in the agrifood sector and broader European cross-sector models. These reference models offer practical lessons on interoperability, trust, and responsible data use, ensuring that SPOON aligns with ongoing European efforts to establish data spaces and federated infrastructures.

The use of reference models serves three main purposes:

- **Alignment:** to ensure SPOON is compatible with European data policies and infrastructures, such as the European Data Strategy and Data Spaces initiatives.
- **Inspiration:** to identify governance practices that can be adapted for citizen-generated food data, for example, from agrifood-focused platforms.
- **Scalability:** to make sure SPOON’s governance framework can be connected with other domains and projects in the future.

Table 5 provides an overview of the external governance models that have been considered. For each model, a brief description and reference link are provided. These examples are not detailed but represent key initiatives relevant to SPOON.

Table 5 External Governance Models

Number	Name	Responsible SPOON Actor
1	DSSC Blueprint (Data Spaces Support Center)	EV ILVO (intergration) and JIBE (technical alignment)

Key features	The DSSC has made a blueprint for data spaces, describing the different elements to consider when building a data space. This blueprint is made on a version basis, each time including more information and updating the framework based on expert and user feedback. The blueprint also includes tools, a glossary, checklists, etc.
Relevance to SPOON	SPOON uses DSSC's layered governance and maturity model as a reference when defining its own governance building blocks (e.g., consent, interoperability, quality).
2	<p>Rulebook model for a fair data economy (version 3.0) EV ILVO (framework) and CSL partners (implementation in labs)</p>
Key features	This rulebook is a guide for creators of data spaces when sharing data. It contains instructions for setting up a data space, a glossary, data space canvas, governance checklist and tools, as well as some agreement templates.
Relevance to SPOON	Helps SPOON define roles and reference structure of the framework for data sharing among partners and citizens.
3	<p>European Commission Data Governance and Data Policies EV ILVO (compliance) and ethics advisory board</p>
Key features	This document presents general data governance principles for secure, ethical, and interoperable data use in EU projects
Relevance to SPOON	Serves as a baseline to ensure SPOON's framework complies with EU expectations on data policy, ethics, openness, and re-use of research data.
4	<p>AgriDataSpace Roadmap EV ILVO (intergration)</p>
Key features	<p>AgriDataSpace was the coordination and support action (finalised April '24) that set out the roadmap for the deployment and operationalisation of CEADS. Thorough mapping of existing data sharing initiatives, governance and business models, technological components and the legal framework have been done, to set out this roadmap, on which the CEADS initiative now can build.</p> <p>It provides a governance framework for data space initiatives that want to participate, and for the data space itself. For more information, please check the roadmap deliverable.</p>

Relevance to SPOON	SPOON aligns its principles and guidelines with AgriDataSpace recommendations, especially on sharing data and connecting with EU data spaces in a trusted way.	
5	CEADS	EV ILVO (integration)
Key features	For CEADS (Common European Agricultural Data Space) the deployment project just started in April, coordinated by EV ILVO, and will develop a data governance framework based on DSSC and AgriDataSpace principles. This work will be followed to align.	
Relevance to SPOON	SPOON follows CEADS governance developments via its partner EV ILVO to ensure citizen food data can interface with CEADS where appropriate.	
6	Gaia-X	JIBE (technical standards), EV ILVO (governance integration)
Key features	Gaia-X aims to establish a decentralized ecosystem of connected cloud services. It allows users to maintain full sovereignty over their data through open standards and transparent governance. They also develop a framework of open standards enabling diverse stakeholders to collaboratively ensure trust, interoperability, and shared governance in data exchanges.	
Relevance to SPOON	SPOON draws on Gaia-X's trust/identity principles to design how citizens authenticate and manage consent in DataU and the Personal Data Wallet.	

5.3.2 Participatory Governance and Co-creation of Rules

Based on the external reference governance models, we are well aware of the importance of engaging the citizens and researchers in the governance and placing them at the forefront of transforming the food system. Also, to align with the citizen science approach, the framework integrates participatory decision-making.

This approach goes beyond simply “consulting” citizens, it actively involves them in shaping the way data is collected, used, and shared. Citizen input directly influences the design of the SPOON digital toolset and the types of questions in the Questionnaire.

Participation doesn't end once data is collected. Citizens may provide their feedback by answering simple questions in the Questionnaire Tool regarding the use of the digital toolset. It is also possible that participants could discuss directly with researchers within the CSLs. CSLs can contribute and give input via workshops/sessions/meetings/emails to suggest improvements regarding the data governance and digital toolset. This helps ensure that data policies, consent processes, and ontologies reflect not just technical requirements, but also the lived experiences of the people contributing the data.

5.3.3 Citizen Rights in Data Use Decisions

SPOON's data governance framework ensures that citizens remain in full control of their own data through a combination of clear rules and practical digital tools. At the core is the DataU platform, a decentralized consent management system that allows participants to decide exactly when, how, and with whom their data is shared. Consent is not a one-time checkbox, it is explicit, dynamic, and revocable, meaning citizens can grant, track, or withdraw permissions at any moment.

To make this control tangible, each participant has access to Dashboard, a place where they can manage their rights on the shared data (consent granting, data updates, consent removal) Besides these, they will also have access to the PDW, a secure, encrypted space for storing and managing personal/sensitive data. The SPOON Dashboard brings all of these applications together in one interface, making it easy for citizens to switch between applications and review what they've shared, adjust their preferences, and see exactly how their contributions are used. Its usability and accessibility will be tested with citizens, including vulnerable groups, to ensure that all participants can effectively exercise their rights in practice.

6 DATA POLICY

6.1 DATA MANAGEMENT

To ensure the trustworthiness and reusability of citizen-generated data, SPOON incorporates provenance and traceability mechanisms directly into its digital workflows. Every dataset collected through the Questionnaire Tool, stored in the SDB and the PDW but only consent to share is given by the citizen via DataU. Through the DashboardU, citizens can view, manage, and modify their data-sharing permissions at any time, ensuring intuitive access for all users. Within SPOON, data provenance is ensured through strict consent and anonymization procedures. Data can only be shared after explicit consent is given via DataU. Any data stored in the SPOON Data Hub must first be anonymized, and this anonymization step itself also requires explicit consent from the original data owner. This directly supports the FAIR principles, ensuring that data is findable and reusable while providing transparency on how it has been collected, transformed, and shared.

For further data flows within the digital toolset, this is described in detail in D2.1 Specifications for the SPOON digital toolset v1.

6.2 DATA QUALITY

6.2.1 Data Quality Dimensions and Standards

Ensuring data quality is essential to the reliability and scientific value of SPOON. The data governance framework defines quality dimensions and establishes validation methods that combine technical aspects with participatory co-development.

To assure high data quality, we will apply:

- **Completeness:** All required fields must be present. For example, the Questionnaire Tool marks key variables as mandatory to ensure that essential data (e.g., consent) is always captured.
- **Accuracy:** Data should reflect real-world conditions. In SPOON, the formats of data are standardized and citizens can report or comment on unusual entries during workshops. Researchers can report them in workshops, meetings, or emails.
- **Consistency:** Standard terminology and codes should be used across datasets. For instance, we have been developing common data ontology and pilot coordinators adopt harmonized formats for demographic variables and food-environment codes, avoiding local variations.
- **Timeliness:** Data should be kept up to date. In SPOON digital toolset, personal data from the Questionnaire Tool will be uploaded immediately to the PDW.
- **Accessibility:** Authorized users should be able to access data in a usable format easily. In SPOON, the Data Hub offers role-based access so researchers and pilot coordinators can retrieve datasets in standard formats.

For example, the Questionnaire Tool enforces data completeness by requiring mandatory fields, while the PDW enables citizens to correct inaccuracies, thereby improving accuracy and logical consistency.

Reference Standards guiding these dimensions include:

Table 6 Reference Standards and Application in SPOON

Standard	Purpose	Application in SPOON
FAIR principles	Make data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable	Guide the DMP and data governance framework; ensure that citizen-generated data can be searched, linked, and reused across EU data spaces.
DCAT-AP (the EU metadata application profile)	EU metadata profile for cataloguing datasets	Metadata for datasets published in the Data Hub follows DCAT-AP, enabling alignment with European data portals.
ISO 8000 (Data quality) and ISO/IEC 11179 (Metadata registries)	International benchmarks for data quality and metadata registries	Provide reference criteria for validating the data quality and metadata in SPOON activities.

These dimensions and standards are not fixed prescriptions but provide a structured foundation. In practice, SPOON will test their applicability in CSLs, refine them with partner input, and adjust to align with evolving European Data Spaces requirements. For example, while ISO references offer useful guidance, implementation will prioritize lightweight, citizen-friendly methods that fit CSL workflows.

6.2.2 Validation and Quality Assurance Methods

SPOON applies iterative validation mechanisms that combine automated checks with community-driven feedback. It combines three-step cycle: automated controls, community validation, and continuous monitoring.

1. Automated Checks (Tool Level)

- **DataU:** Consent collected from citizens is immutably logged on the blockchain to create a tamper-proof record. ProxyU ensures encrypted data transfer to safeguard integrity. (JIBE)
- **Questionnaire Tool:** It enforces structured formats and built-in validation, preventing errors at the point of entry. Responses are stored directly in PDW and the SPOON Database, linking them transparently to user consent. (JIBE)
- **Data HuB:** Stores only anonymized data, with anonymization carried out deliberately by researchers. The data will be formatted standardly and accessed publicly by researchers. (Pilot implementers (CSLs and BCIs); Coordinators of CSLs and BCIs; Impact measurement lead)

2. Community Validation (Citizen & Partner Level)

- **PDW:** Serves as a citizen-controlled validation layer. Individuals can review, correct, and categorize their own information, ensuring accuracy and logical organization. (Pilot implementers (CSLs and BCIs), supported by citizens)
- **Dashboard:** Offers unified, role-based access and presents quality indicators (e.g., completeness scores, anomaly flags). Feedback loops allow users to highlight issues, supporting continuous improvement. (Pilot implementers (CSLs and BCIs); Coordinators of CSLs and BCIs; Impact measurement lead)
- **Co-development & Feedback Loops:** workshops, sessions, and ticketing support allow pilot coordinators and implementers as well as other researchers in the project, including users to suggest improvements; optional short surveys may capture citizen feedback. (Pilot implementers (CSLs and BCIs); Coordinators of CSLs and BCIs; Impact measurement lead; Citizens; JIBE)

3. Monitoring & Evaluation (Project Level)

- **Monitoring & Evaluation:** WP5 delivers a monitoring toolkit and implements formative evaluations with multiple feedback loops. This consolidates automated quality checks and community input into a unified evaluation process.

6.3 DATA INTEROPERABILITY

Interoperability is central to the European Data Spaces initiative, defined as the capacity to exchange, understand, and reuse data across systems (European Union, 2017).

For the SPOON digital toolset ecosystem to function effectively, data must not only be high quality but also interoperable across tools and external systems. The toolset achieves this through several key measures:

- **Standardized Data Formats:** Datasets in the Data Hub are described in JSON-LD, RDF, or other standardized formats, ensuring compatibility with semantic web technologies.
- **Open Standards and Ontologies:** SPOON aligns with existing food and health ontologies, enabling seamless integration and reuse across EU projects.
- **API Interoperability:** All APIs follow OpenAPI standards, ensuring that third-party applications and research platforms can interact reliably with SPOON data.
- **EU Data Spaces Integration:** The Questionnaire Tool, PDW, DataU, Data HUB, and Dashboard are natively integrated and align with initiatives such as GAIA-X, FOOD2030, and DjustConnect. So, data flows smoothly without redundancy or fragmentation.

6.4 DATA SHARING

The DGA highlights that data sharing needs to be framed as cross-sectoral innovation and protecting citizen rights (European Union, 2025). Research infrastructures increasingly emphasise open science platforms (e.g., Zenodo, Open Research Europe) as trusted channels for compliant data dissemination.

SPOON adopts a principled, citizen-centric approach to data sharing. Citizens decide whether their data is shared, under what conditions, and whether it remains personal or becomes anonymised for public research.

- **Personal Data Sharing:** When shared via PDW, data remains encrypted and under citizen control, with consent managed through DataU.
- **Anonymized Data:** Data Hub hosts only anonymised, consented datasets, which are made available for open research.
- **Trusted Dissemination Channels:** Outputs, besides the Data Hub, will also be published on recognised open platforms such as Zenodo and Open Research Europe, ensuring GDPR appliance and FAIR principles.

7 DATA ONTOLOGY

Technical interoperability relies on common standards (JSON-LD, RDF, OpenAPI), while semantic interoperability requires ontologies and controlled vocabularies. Agrifood-related projects (e.g., FoodOn, DEMETER) have demonstrated how shared ontologies enable consistent categorisation across diverse datasets.

7.1 DEFINITION AND PURPOSE

WHAT DO WE MEAN BY ‘ONTOLOGY’?

The term ‘ontology’ comes from the field of philosophy, which talks about a theory of the nature of existence (Lowe, 2005). However, the scientific researchers had adopted this term with the modern technological development. An ontology is a structured representation of knowledge about a specific domain, defining concepts, properties, and relationships between them (Tom Gruber, 2016).

In this document, an ontology is a formal, shared vocabulary of concepts and their relations to describe citizen-generated data, which enables researchers to interpret data consistently across activities, regions and different food environments. In contrast, data standards like JSON-LD and OpenAPI govern how data is exchanged; they don’t define a shared meaning on their own.

WHY SPOON NEEDS ONE?

With multiple pilot regions, activities, questionnaires, and APPs feeding the SPOON digital toolset, a common vocabulary is essential to:

- Harmonize data collection and labels across sites and languages,
- Support understandable and reusable data across tools, labs and countries by stakeholders,
- Support interoperability with other EU initiatives (e.g., GAIA-X, and FOOD2030)

7.2 SELECTED ONTOLOGIES AND VOCABULARIES

SPOON will adopt and align with the following (scope summarized for our use):

- **FoodOn:** Comprehensive food ontology (ingredients, products, processing, packaging). Good backbone for “what is being consumed” and for harmonizing item lists across CSL questionnaires.
- **AGROVOC (FAO):** Multilingual SKOS thesaurus covering agriculture, food and nutrition; useful for broader agrifood terms and multilingual labels; includes domain sub-vocabularies like LandVoc.
- **DEMETER AIM:** DEMETER’s Agriculture Information Model reuses FoodOn/AGROVOC/SAREF4AGRI; we will mirror that reuse-first strategy and map where helpful.

- **INRAE Thesaurus** (via AgroPortal / Vocabulaires Ouverts INRAE): A shared, open thesaurus is developed by the French National Research Institute for Agriculture, Food and the Environment (INRAE). It contains over 16,000 concepts, including food systems, environmental methods, and research-related terminology.

7.3 SPOON ONTOLOGY

In addition to referencing and aligning with reference ontologies such as FoodOn, AGROVOC, DEMETER AIM, and INRAE Thesaurus, we propose a dedicated ontology categories tailored to the specific needs of project research activities (CSLs, BCIs) and the SPOON digital toolset. This ontology serves as a shared vocabulary for representing citizen-generated food data in a structured and interoperable way.

The initial proposal (V1) defines the following **core categories**, illustrated in [Figure 5](#). It's worth noting that, apart from Food Product Type and Food Environment, the other categories could be more likely to involve personal or sensitive information. This distinction shows which categories in the ontology need stricter consent, anonymization, and protection measures, in line with GDPR principles.

Figure 5 SPOON Ontology Categories

The table below (Table 7) shows the definitions of each ontology category with some simple examples.

Table 7 Definitions of SPOON ontology categories

Category	Definition	Example
Food Product Type	Describes what the data is about in terms of food items or preparations.	Carrot, lasagna recipe, breakfast cereal box
Food Environment	Information about where people obtain or consume food. Covers both physical and digital environments.	Restaurant, supermarket, canteen, vending machine, online delivery app
Demographic Information	Basic socio-demographic descriptions of participants.	Age, gender, household composition, socio-economic background
Health and Nutrition	Data about people's health status, dietary requirements, or nutrient intake that may influence or result from food choices.	BMI, allergy to peanuts, daily fibre intake, Nutri-Score
Dietary Habits	Patterns of eating: how often, how much, and in what form foods are consumed.	Meal timing, portion size, weekly frequency of fish
Consumer Preferences	What people like or value in food, and their self-reported choices. Focuses on perceptions and attitudes.	Taste liking, price sensitivity
Consumer Behavior	Observable actions or decisions people make in food contexts.	Shopping routine, impulse purchases
User Group / Actor Type	The role or stakeholder type of the data contributor or user inside SPOON and the wider food system.	Citizen, policymaker, researcher

This draft ontology backbone provides the starting point for harmonizing data across project pilot regions and the Digital Toolset. It will be further validated and refined through stakeholder workshops and iterative feedback during project implementation.

7.4 STAKEHOLDER INPUT AND ITERATIVE REFINEMENT

Because ontology development is inherently **iterative and participatory**, the categories, defined in V1, are not final. They will be validated, refined, and expanded through stakeholder input and real-world application during the project. The methodological approach to be implemented in the pilot regions is being refined and the ontology categories and further specifications will be adapted to that work, in an interactive way. Literature on ontology engineering emphasizes that domain ontologies should evolve together in the context of a task, incorporating stakeholder knowledge, real-world application feedback, and keeping it alive to shape the content (Kotis et al., 2020). Particularly in food and citizen science contexts, ontologies should be co-created with stakeholders through structured workshops and iterative refinements, ensuring that vocabularies capture the diversity of real-world practices while maintaining alignment with broader interoperability frameworks (Buyle et al., 2016; Dooley et al., 2018; Weber et al., 2023). In SPOON, this process will be carried out primarily through CSLs and exchanges with food decision makers, where stakeholders will co-create and test ontology categories/classes/properties in practice. This means that ontology categories will be reviewed in CSL workshops, adjusted based on the citizen-generated food data they capture, and refined to ensure interoperability with external frameworks.

APPLICATION IN SPOON

For SPOON, ontology development will be treated as a living repository, refined in close collaboration with stakeholders across the project. This ontology not only reflects theoretical concepts but also responds to the evolving needs of the pilots and the broader Digital Toolset. For as far as they exist for the SPOON categories, we will start from existing ontology classifications, and adapt these where necessary to the needs of the project.

PLANNED ITERATIONS (ALIGNED WITH SPOON TOOLSET):

Figure 6 Planned iteration timeline for ontology

- V1 (short-term, M1–M10): Develop a SPOON ontology backbone, and place a solid foundation for further research and development.
- V1–V1.5 (mid-term, M10–M24): Ontology validation and expansion through stakeholder workshops, incorporating new food items, contextual dimensions, and methodological refinements. Each ontology release (e.g., V1, V1.5) will be documented through a formal change log that records stakeholder input and feedback, and decisions made during

workshops. Version control will be maintained through the project's shared repository, allowing all partners to access current and past versions.

- V2 (final, M24–M30): An inclusive SPOON ontology that is validated and aligned with interoperability standards.

WORKSHOPS

- **First Input Round:** Pilot partners will be engaged via interactive polls and structured discussions to identify and validate main ontology categories, such as Food Product, Food Environment, Demographic, User Group, Health, Dietary Habits, and Consumer Consumption. These categories will provide feedback to the backbone of V1. And we will also encourage all project partners to brainstorm the potential classes and properties for the data ontology. Then the results will be integrated into the V1.
- **Future Workshops:** A series of workshops will be held, each involving a distinct stakeholder group identified through a stakeholder mapping activity. Each workshop will discuss with different stakeholders such as pilot implementers, ontology or technical experts, and researchers involving in the project, etc. These will ensure that the ontology captures both technical interoperability needs and social/behavioral aspects of food data. The workshops will also function as co-design spaces for iterative ontology refinement. The workshops timeline will be planned in detail and updated in the next version of the deliverable.

8 SECURITY AND ACCESS CONTROL

8.1 DATA SECURITY MEASURES AND ACCESS CONTROL

In SPOON, data security follows the **CIA triad**. It is a foundational model in information security, emphasizing three essential pillars: confidentiality, integrity, and availability. Confidentiality safeguards information from unauthorized access, integrity ensures that data remains accurate and reliable, and availability guarantees that authorized users can access the information whenever it is needed.

In SPOON, it is operationalized through the design of the digital toolset, please refer to Table 8 for further information.

Table 8 SPOON Data Security Measures (CIA Triad)

Principle	Definition	SPOON Application
Confidentiality	Protecting data from unauthorized access or disclosure.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Personal data in PDW encrypted at rest and in transit • Role-based access control in Dashboard • Consent cryptographically logged in DataU (blockchain)
Integrity	Ensuring accuracy, consistency, and protection from unauthorized modification or deletion.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Questionnaire Tool validates inputs before storage • Provenance metadata ensures verifiable data history and prevents manipulation
Availability	Guaranteeing reliable access to data for authorized users when needed.	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • ProxyU ensures secure, reliable data transfer • Separate applications designed with redundancy and recoverability • Requests routed via DataU with secure peer-to-peer connections

Each of the tools is developed as a separate application with the CIA triad in mind. Each request for data in principle goes via DataU, and after consent is given, a secure peer-to-peer connection is set up between the proxyU of the application and Dashboard. In this way, the data sharing also follows the CIA triad principle.

8.2 DATA PROTECTION

Data protection in SPOON ensures that personal data is handled lawfully, ethically, and transparently in compliance with GDPR, DGA, the Data Act, and other relevant EU regulations. These measures will be maintained by the SPOON digital toolset developer JIBE.

Key measures include:

- **Authentication & Authorisation:** Multi-factor authentication (MFA) for system administrators and secure logins for all users.
- **Data Encryption:** All communication between tools (e.g., Questionnaire Tool → PDW → Data Hub) uses access tokens. Sensitive data in the PDW is encrypted at rest, while anonymized datasets in the Data Hub are stored securely. This safeguards confidentiality and supports the right to data security.
- **Integrity & Provenance Validation:** Blockchain-based logging in DataU creates immutable records of consent, strengthening transparency and auditability. This ensures citizens can verify how their consent has been applied.
- **Data Minimisation:** In line with GDPR principles, the Questionnaire Tool collects only essential data. The PDW enables citizens to exercise their rights to access, rectification, erasure, and portability, by reviewing, correcting, or exporting their personal information, and controlling its sharing.

8.3 RISK MANAGEMENT

The SPOON project implements a comprehensive approach to risk management, centrally coordinated through the project management line of work. This ensures that risks related to data security, privacy, and ethical use are continuously monitored and mitigated. Based on that, the SPOON digital toolset implements a structured risk management approach to anticipate, monitor, and mitigate threats to data security and privacy.

Risks are categorized into:

- **Technical risks:** e.g., cyberattacks, data corruption, infrastructure failures.
- **Process risks:** e.g., incorrect consent handling, lack of timely data anonymization.
- **Human risks:** e.g., insider threats, accidental data disclosure.

Mitigation measures include Documented Protocols, Incident Response Plan, and Continuous Monitoring. This part will be further detailed and refined as the SPOON digital toolset develops and pilot activities progress. We will make sure that risk management measures remain effective and aligned with evolving project needs and European standards.

9 ETHICS AND PRIVACY

9.1 ETHICAL PRINCIPLES

The activities follow European ethical regulations and relevant national ethics standards. Each pilot partner secures local ethics approval before starting recruitment or data collection, recording the approval details in the DMP and updating them regularly.

The project prioritizes:

- **Participant protection:** safeguarding privacy, avoiding unnecessary risk, and ensuring non-discrimination. All demographic groups have equal opportunity to participate. The project confirms that it involves human participants who are volunteers for non-medical studies and potentially vulnerable individuals or groups.
- **Personal data:** SPOON empowers users with unparalleled control over their personal data. The DataU platform serves as a decentralized, GDPR-compliant consent management system that no personal data is stored or controlled by DataU itself; instead, data remains with the processors who collect it. The PDW acts as a secure, encrypted repository where citizens can store, manage, and selectively share their food-related/personal data.
- **AI ethics:** any AI-based analysis is checked for fairness, transparency, explainability, and bias. Data analysis will, where possible, be supported by the use of open-source AI tools. Specific tools are to be determined during the data analysis phase by pilot implementers and other project partners.

9.2 DATA PRIVACY

Data privacy in SPOON follows the data minimization and privacy-by-design principles: only what is needed is collected, and personal data stays under participant control.

Anonymization/pseudonymization

The SPOON Data Hub is designated as a repository for anonymized datasets. Data enters the Data Hub only with the explicit consent of citizens for its anonymization. When full anonymization is not yet possible, pseudonymization is applied as an interim step. Pseudonymization replaces identifying details with codes but still allows re-identification under controlled conditions, while anonymization irreversibly removes all links to individuals. In practice, project partners and researchers apply pseudonymization during data collection and early processing, whereas technical partners are responsible for carrying out anonymization procedures before data is transferred into the Data Hub.

Data storage

Personal data is never centralized; Citizens can decide if they want to share their personal data via PDW by approving consent on DataU. In this part, the digital toolset ensures secure storage in the PDW and role-based access control, while citizens are supported in understanding and exercising their choices.

9.3 CONSENT MANAGEMENT AND DATA MINIMIZATION

Informed consent forms are distributed to all participants before activities and tool usage where research data is collected. DataU operates on a peer-to-peer (P2P) network, ensuring that data sovereignty remains with the data subject. Through Dashboard, citizens have a user-friendly interface to view, manage, and modify their data-sharing permissions at any time. Consent is explicit, dynamic, and revocable.

When citizens use the Questionnaire Tool, they provide answers with consent, which are then stored in their PDW. Third-party applications wishing to connect to DataU must obtain explicit consent from citizens to access and process personal data.

The DataU platform is designed to support the principle of data minimisation, ensuring that personal data is only collected and processed when genuinely necessary. The project conducts a thorough evaluation to determine when and why personal data is truly required, prioritising data minimisation and privacy-by-design principles.

10 CONCLUSION

This deliverable has outlined the foundations of the SPOON data governance framework, focusing on data strategy, data policy, security, interoperability, ontology, and ethics. A central principle has been to ensure that citizen-generated food data via digital toolset is collected, stored, and shared in a way that is trustworthy, transparent, and aligned with European values and regulations.

In conclusion, this first version of the framework:

- **Data security and protection protocols (GDPR compliance):**
Establishes layered consent management through the PDW and DataU, ensuring explicit and informed consent. GDPR principles (lawfulness, fairness, transparency, data minimization, storage limitation) are embedded into every data flow.
- **High data quality standards and interoperability:**
Proposes initial validation mechanisms and the adoption of open standards, APIs, and a draft ontology backbone to support harmonization across CSLs and with external initiatives.
- **Ethical and privacy challenges in Citizen Science:**
Promotes ethical participation by safeguarding personal data, ensuring inclusiveness in CSLs, and embedding transparency and accountability in all interactions. Privacy-by-design is applied in toolset development and stakeholder engagement.
- **Integration with European Data Spaces and digital infrastructures:**
Identifies pathways for alignment with GAIA-X, DjustConnect, and emerging agri-food data spaces, while recognizing that technical and governance connections will need to be further developed.

At the same time, certain components remain in an early stage. The ontology is currently at v1 and will need iterative refinement with stakeholders. The choice and integration of AI ethics tools are still under discussion. Mechanisms for long-term interoperability and scaling across European infrastructures also require further specification.

By explicitly addressing these objectives, the data governance framework provides the foundation for a reliable and scalable SPOON digital ecosystem. It ensures that citizens, researchers, and policymakers can confidently engage with the collected data while contributing to the long-term goal of creating a more sustainable and inclusive European food system.

Looking ahead, the next iterations of this framework (M10–M30) will focus on operational refinement: expanding the ontology repository with stakeholders' input, integrating feedback from project partners and stakeholders, and delivering a scalable, citizen-centered, and future-proof model for responsible food data sharing in Europe. These developments will be documented in **the interim versions of this deliverable (internal)** and further consolidated in **Deliverable D2.5 – SPOON Data Report v2**, ensuring that progress is transparently aligned with project milestones.

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